

Indium-induced ultrasound-mediated rearrangement of β -lactam to oxazines

Ram Naresh Yadav^a, Susanta Samjadar^b and Bimal Krishna Banik*^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Veer Bahadur Singh Purvanchal University, Jaunpur-222 003, Uttar Pradesh

^bDepartment of Molecular Pathology, The University of Texas-M. D. Anderson Cancer Center, 1515 Holcombe Blvd., Houston, Texas 77030, USA

^cDepartment of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, College of Sciences and Human Studies, Prince Mohammad Bin Fahd University, Al Khobar, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

E-mail: bimalbanik10@gmail.com, bbanik@pmu.edu.sa

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The regiospecific intramolecular nucleophilic ring opening (INRO) of 2-azetidinones through ultrasound-mediated indium metal/ammonium chloride-induced reduction of aromatic nitro functionality has been achieved at ambient temperature. This method has provided an efficient entry for the facile synthesis of benzo[1,4]-oxazine-2-one derivatives in aqueous ethanol.

Keywords: Nitro β -lactam, indium, ultrasound, rearrangement, oxazine.

Introduction

Synthetic study on β -lactam has been extensively studied since over a century in connection with a quest thriving their biological and medicinal properties as antibiotics and enzyme inhibitory activity¹. Owing to greater ring strain (25 kcal/mol) and regioselective cleavage of β -lactam ring makes β -lactams as potential synthetic precursors in organic synthesis of medicinally privileged molecules²⁻⁴. It is widely known that N¹-C(O) bond of the β -lactam ring undergoes facile cleavage with nucleophiles even with water. Using the advantage of this cleavage Wasserman demonstrated an elegant methodology in the total synthesis of the macrocyclic ring alkaloids^{5,6}. However, other possibilities using β -lactam rings have been also explored. Remarkably, Ojima and our group demonstrated that N¹-C⁴ bond of β -lactam ring can be exclusively cleaved under heterogeneous catalytic hydro-genolysis when an aryl substituent is present at C3 position of the β -lactam ring^{7,8}. The main driving force of this reaction is attributed owing to ring strain accompanied with β -lactam ring⁹. This outstanding discovery added the new tool box in synthetic organic chemistry for easy synthesis of unusual aromatic α -hydroxy acid, α -amino acids, dipeptides, polyamino alcohols and polyamino ethers.

The regioselective Bronsted/Lewis acid-mediated ring opening/cyclization of N¹-C(O) bond (intramolecular acyl migration) of N-aryl β -lactams has provided an efficient and economical protocol for the synthesis of quinolone-4(1H)-one¹⁰⁻¹². Based on the strategy, Dong *et al.* reported very elegant synthetic approach toward 3-spirocyclicquinolin-4(1H)-ones by Bronsted-Lewis acids in combination with super acid solution¹³.

Benzo[1,4]-oxazines are important heterocyclic motifs with a wide range of pharmacological properties¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Owing to their wide range of pharmacological activities, they received attention of many researchers to develop new synthetic strategies to access these unique molecules. The pioneer studies for the synthesis of 1,4-oxazine included metal-free cascade cyclization of epoxy yanamides¹⁷, silver(I)-catalyzed intramolecular annulation of propargylic ester epoxide¹⁸ and Rh(II)/Mg-catalyzed tandem reaction of triazole-glycidol annulations¹⁹.

We envisioned metal-induced intramolecular reductive ring opening of β -lactam through N¹-C(O) bond cleavage could be a new synthetic method for the facile accesses oxazine derivatives. In this context we performed an elegant syn-

thesis of oxazines by indium-induced reductive-rearrangement of the nitro β -lactams in aqueous ethanol under thermal conditions²⁰.

Herein we report ultrasound-mediated indium metal-induced reductive rearrangement of aryl amino β -lactams to benzo[1,4]-oxazine derivatives through an intramolecular nucleophilic N¹-C(O) bond cleavage of β -lactam rings.

Results and discussion

In our earlier report, we have employed indium-induced reductive cyclization to diverse heterocyclic motif of biologically relevance molecules^{21–23}. In continuation of our efforts on the synthesis of anticancer β -lactams and metal-induced cyclization reactions, we studied application of indium metal-induced reaction in the synthesis of diverse organic compounds of medicinal interest^{24,25}.

In this context we studied a selective reduction of the diverse aromatic nitro compounds **1a–d** to aromatic amines **2a–d** by indium metal and ammonium chloride in refluxing aqueous ethanol (Scheme 1, Table 1). The time required for the completion of the reaction was greatly depended on the nature of the substituents present in the aromatic ring and in general, it varied from 10–80 h. The reaction with highly functionalized aromatic nitro compound **2d** was sluggish and required long reaction time with moderate yield. This was attributed due to the presence of the methyl group at the

Scheme 1. In⁰ metal induced reduction of aromatic nitro group reduction under thermal condition^a.

Table 1. Reduction under thermal condition^a

2	X	Y	Z	Time (h)	Yield ^b (%)
a	F	H	H	10	80
b	Cl	H	H	8	90
c	H	H	CN	5	85
d	H	Me	Br	80	50

^aReaction was performed in 1 mmol scale at 80°C. ^bIsolated yield.

ortho position with respect to the NO₂ group which may cause steric hindrance during the reduction process (Table 1, entry 2d).

The preliminary results were inspiring and encouraged us to modify the reaction conditions further to obtain the products with an improved yield under milder reaction conditions. For this purpose, we decided to perform the reaction under ultrasound wave (strength of 40 KHz and 600 W energy) in an automated sonicator (Scheme 2, Table 2).

Scheme 2. In⁰ metal induced reduction of aromatic nitro functionality under ultrasound irradiation.

Table 2. Reduction under thermal condition^a

2	X	Y	Z	Time (min)	Yield (%)
a	F	H	H	30	90
b	Cl	H	H	20	95
c	H	H	CN	10	90
d	H	Me	Br	60	80

Surprisingly the reaction went very smoothly with high yield in shorter reaction time. As discussed earlier under thermal condition the reduction of the substrate **1d** was very slow. However, under ultrasonication, the reaction time for this substrate was reduced considerably. On comparison the results delineated in Table 1 and Table 2, it was important to note that ultrasound-mediated reaction results are more promising. The exact reason for this incredible enhancement of reaction rate is under investigation. We envisioned that ultrasonication helps to reduce the particle size of the indium powder further so to enable additional surface areas which turn to enhance the reducing ability of the metal^{26,27}. It worthy to note that in recent years, the application of ultrasound wave in organic synthesis has received tremendous attention by the scientific community. The use of ultrasound wave has been proven an alternative tool to synthesize di-

Scheme 3. Model reaction of indium metal induced 2'-nitro-[1,1'-biphenyl]-2-carbaldehyde annulation to phenanthridine under thermal and ultrasound irradiation.

verse class of organic molecules of medicinal and pharmaceutical interests^{28–34}.

Under the stated conditions, we next investigated the scope of one-pot reductive cyclization of 2-nitro-[1,1'-biphenyl]-2-carbaldehyde to phenanthridine **4** (Scheme 3). As shown in Scheme 3 synthesis of phenanthridine **4** was achieved in high yield under ultrasound irradiation.

The synthesis of benzo oxazines from nitro-substituted β -lactams via reductive nucleophilic rearrangement strategy following the above method was the next target. 2-(2-Nitrophenoxy) acetyl chloride **5** was used as ketene precursor in cycloaddition reaction in the synthesis of the desired β -lactams.

Initially, 2-(2-nitrophenoxy) acetyl chloride **5** and imine **6a** derived from the condensation of benzaldehyde and aniline were annulated to *cis* and *trans* 2-azetidione **7a** and **8a** (Scheme 4) in 80% yield. It was worthy to note that the stereochemistry of the products is greatly depended on the substitution patterns of the imines and the mode of the addition of the reagents.

Interestingly, the slow addition of nitro phenoxy acetyl chloride **6** to the solution of imine containing Et₃N in anhydrous dichloromethane at -78°C favored the exclusive for-

mation of *rac*-(+/-)-*cis*- β -lactam **7** in excellent yield (Scheme 4, Route a). But, under microwave irradiation (Scheme 3, Route b) at 80°C , formation of the corresponding *rac*-(+/-)-*trans*- β -lactam **8** was observed³⁵.

Following our standardized protocol, we synthesized diverse *cis* and *trans*- β -lactams in good to excellent yield (Tables 3 and 4).

After the successful synthesis of β -lactam precursors we next focused to ultrasound-assisted synthesis of benzo[1,4]-oxazines. The β -lactams **7** and **8** were allowed to react in aqueous ethanol, ammonium chloride and indium powder. These mixtures were irradiated with ultrasound wave for 10–20 min. Following our expectation reduction of nitro functionality followed by concomitant nucleophilic ring opening rearrangement to oxazine derivatives took place in good yield (at room temperature) (Scheme 5 and 6 and Tables 5 and 6).

The reduction of nitro function to amino groups and its nucleophilic attack to the amide carbonyl group of β -lactam ring were the key reactions of the rearrangement process to benzo [1,4]-oxazine. The nucleophilicity of the amino functionality was further augmented by the coordination of indium metal to the amide groups. It was attributed due to the

Scheme 4. Synthesis of aryl nitro substituted β -lactam via Staudinger ketene-Imine [2+2] cycloaddition reaction.

Table 3. Synthesis of *cis*- β -lactam under thermal condition

Entry	X	Z	3R/4R [7]	Yield (%)
1	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	7a	80
2	C ₆ H ₅	4(MeO)C ₆ H ₅	7b	90
3	C ₆ H ₅	4(Me)C ₆ H ₅	7c	85
4	C ₆ H ₅	4(F)C ₆ H ₅	7d	80
5	4(Me)C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	7e	85

^aReaction were performed in 1 mmol scale.

Table 4. Synthesis of *trans*- β -lactam under microwave condition^a

Entry	X	Z	3R/4S [8]	Yield ^b (%)
1	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	8a	90
2	C ₆ H ₅	4(MeO)C ₆ H ₅	8b	90
3	C ₆ H ₅	4(Me)C ₆ H ₅	8c	85
4	C ₆ H ₅	4(F)C ₆ H ₅	8d	85
5	C ₆ H ₅	4(Me)C ₆ H ₅	8e	90

^bIsolated yield.

Table 5. Synthesis of *cis*-benzo[1,4]-oxazine under ultrasound irradiation

Entry	X	Z	3R/4R [7]	Yield (%)
1	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	9a	70
2	C ₆ H ₅	4(MeO)C ₆ H ₅	9b	75
3	C ₆ H ₅	4(Me)C ₆ H ₅	9c	80
4	C ₆ H ₅	4(F)C ₆ H ₅	9d	80
5	4(Me)C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	9e	85

Table 6. Synthesis of *trans*-benzo[1,4]-oxazine under ultrasound irradiation^a

Entry	X	Z	3R/4S [8]	Yield ^b (%)
1	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	10a	65
2	C ₆ H ₅	4(MeO)C ₆ H ₅	10b	70
3	C ₆ H ₅	4(Me)C ₆ H ₅	10c	80
4	C ₆ H ₅	4(F)C ₆ H ₅	10d	85
5	C ₆ H ₅	4(Me)C ₆ H ₅	10e	80

Scheme 5. Ultrasound mediated synthesis bezo[1,4]-oxazine via reductive rearrangement of *cis*- β -lactams.

Scheme 6. Ultrasound mediated synthesis bezo[1,4]-oxazine via reductive rearrangement of *trans*- β -lactams.

Scheme 6. Mechanistic overview.

oxophilic nature of the indium metal^{36–38}. This was further supported by our additional experiments. For example, the reductive cyclization was performed in the presence of Zn/NH₄Cl or Sn/NH₄Cl. Surprisingly, exclusive reduction of the nitro group was observed and there was no cyclization to benzo[1,4]-oxazines. Based on this result we envisioned that indium metal-induced reaction was not only reduce the nitro group, but it also clicks the ring opening of the lactam ring through nucleophilic attack and leads the formation of the desired products. The plausible sequences of the mechanistic outcome of this transformation are likely to proceed as follows (Scheme 6). Initially the indium metal coordinated with the (CO)-N¹ bond followed by the nucleophilic attack of NH₂ group to form dianionic intermediate (I) which was subsequently transformed to intermediate (II) by cleavage of

(CO)-N¹ bond followed by the abstraction of proton that delivered the target benzo[1,4]-oxazine.

Conclusions

A facile preparation of diversely substituted oxazines is developed through an intramolecular-rearrangement reaction of amino β -lactams in the presence of ultrasound. This method is also suitable for the preparation of other analogues in this series.

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